

Annex to: Scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and defrosting of frozen ungulates meat. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2026.9825

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Annex D – Additional a_w values in meat gathered from different ungulate species

Table D.2. reports additional bibliographic references supporting the water activity (a_w) scenarios established for standard fresh meat in the EFSA opinion on aged meat (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2023) and used also within this opinion.

Table D.2. Reported a_w values in different ungulate species at different points of the stabilisation period and after the stabilisation period.

Animal species	a_w at different points (hours) of stabilisation period	a_w at different points (days) after stabilisation period	Reference
Bovine	24h post-mortem: 0.965 (aerobic) – 0.967 (anaerobic)	8 days post-mortem: 0.964 (aerobic) – 0.969 (anaerobic) 15 d: 0.964 (aerobic) – 0.967 (anaerobic) 22 d: 0.964 (aerobic) – 0.966 (anaerobic) 29 d: 0.962 (aerobic) – 0.963 (anaerobic)	Kahraman and Gurbuz, 2019
Bovine		18 d post-mortem: \approx 0.965 41 d: \approx 0.964	Smaldone et al., 2019
Bovine	\approx 1h post-mortem: 0.991 (lean meat at 4°C) \approx 7h: 0.986 \approx 17h: 0.995 \approx 25h: 0.983	\approx 31h: 0.988 \approx 41h: 0.977 \approx 49h: 0.980 \approx 55h: 0.984 \approx 65h: 0.977 \approx 73h: 0.983	Crowley et al., 2009
Bovine	0h: 0.98-0.99 24h: 0.98-0.99 48h: 0.95-0.99		McSharry et al., 2021a
Bovine	1h of chilling carcass: 0.97 24h of chilling: 0.96 48h of chilling: 0.96	72h of chilling: 0.97 96h of chilling: 0.96 0 week of chilling primals (anaerobic): 0.96 1 w: 0.95 2 w: 0.93 3 w: 0.95 4 w: 0.94 5 w: 0.96 6 w: 0.95	Reid et al., 2017
Bovine	0-66 days	Values provided within a figure in the publication	McSharry et al. 2021b
Ovine	1 day post-mortem: 0.996	3d: 0.958 7d: 0.955	Cetin et al., 2012
Ovine	1h post-mortem: 0.94 24h: 0.96	48h: 0.90 96h: 0.89	Ortega et al., 2016

Porcine	1 day post-mortem: 0.976	7 days post-mortem: 0.975 10 days: 0.976	Duma-Kocan et al., 2023
Porcine	1 day post-mortem: 0.98-0.99		Bermudez et al., 2017
Porcine	1 day post-mortem: 0.990	3 days post-mortem: 0.990 7d: 0.990 12d: 0.992 15d: 0.990	Bruckner et al., 2012

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